

Biotechnology in Floral Industry

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Introduction

The floriculture industry has grown rapidly around the world, especially in developing countries, thanks to low maintenance costs, which include low labour costs. Consumer demand for new value-added flowers that are both cost effective and special in flower characteristics must be met by the industry. As a result, a major aim in floriculture is to grow new ornamental cultivars with improved floral attributes.

Many ornamental plant varieties have been developed using biotechnological methods such as tissue culture and micropropagation techniques, polyploidy induction, mutation breeding, and genetic engineering. Biotechnology can be used to create plants with novel characteristics such as floral architecture, colour, fragrance, abiotic stress tolerance, and post-harvest life.

Biotechnological Approach

Micropropagation: Tissue culture has been widely used for disease-free floriculture seed multiplication and propagation (Mousavi et al., 2012). Genotype, medium, sugars, growth regulators, explant type, and other factors all have an impact on tissue culture propagation efficiency (Miri et al., 2016).

Somaclonal variation: The potential of somaclonal variation as a source for cultivar growth has been debated since its discovery in the 1970s. Somaclonal variation has been a significant source for floriculture crop cultivar growth. This group of crops produces somaclonal variants in vitro that may be novel and can be fixed through vegetative propagation (Chen et al., 2006).

Polyloid Breeding: Ploidy manipulation has long been thought to be a useful method for improving ornamental characteristics and making breeding programmes easier (Roughani et al., 2017).

Mutation: In order to develop crops, any plant breeding programme must include genetic variation. Induced mutation has been used to produce diversity and breeding in plants. Gamma rays are one of the most widely used mutagens for inducing mutations (Rahbar et al., 2015).

Genetic Modification: Although traditional breeding programmes have been very effective in producing novel flowers, genetic modification provides new avenues for the development of important floricultural plants (Chandler et al., 2012).

It is very likely that disease resistance and stress tolerance genes will be introduced into ornamental plant species (Noman et al., 2017). The majority of ornamental species transformation protocols depend on Agrobacterium-mediated gene transfer and particle bombardment (Aragao et al., 2006).

Role of Biotechnology for Modifications in Floral Characteristics

Flower colour: The colour of the flowers is one of the most significant characteristics of many ornamental plants (Chandler et al., 2012). Anthocyanins, flavonoids, carotenoids, and betalains are the main pigments responsible for the beauty of flower colours.

The genetics of plant species restrict colour range, and genetic modification is the only effective way to resolve this restriction. After transferring some primary genes for the carotenoid biosynthesis pathway under 35S CaMV, Azadi et al. (2010) confirmed numerous pigments in transgenic lilly calli and leaves. CmCCD4a is a gene

found only in the white chrysanthemum ray petals. This is a single dominant gene that prevents carotenoids from forming or accumulating in petals.

A rose mutant called 'Wouburn Gold' was discovered to have the highest levels of flavanol, anthocyanin, leucoanthocyanin, and complete carotenoid, resulting in tangerine orange petal colour (Patil et al., 2009).

Induction of early flowering: The MADS box gene family, such as AP1, regulates flowering time and floral organ production. AP1 overexpression during short days in transgenic chrysanthemums will start bud initiation 14 days earlier than non-transgenic plants. The GSQUA2 gene was transformed in Gerbera to speed up flowering (Noman et al., 2017).

Flower morphology and plant architecture: Overexpression of the tobacco phytochrome b1 gene in chrysanthemum resulted in small plants with greater branch angles. Later, the Arabidopsis GA insensitive gene was used to reduce the height of chrysanthemum plants.

Transgenic carnations with the rol C gene and the 35S CaMV promoter showed increased stem cutting production, flowering stems, and root organogenesis (Noman et al., 2017). Rahbar et al., (2015) found that gamma irradiated gloxinia plantlets had fluffy leaves, funnel-shaped leaves, small internodes, colour changes, and double-flowered flowers.

Fragrance engineering: Many terpenoid, phenylpropanoid/benzenoid, and aromatic amino acid volatiles are used in floral scents (Noman et al., 2017). Key genes involved in the development and control of fragrance have been established (Chandler et al., 2012), and the use of genetic engineering to manipulate scent genes has resulted in the successful implementation of this technology for enhancing floral scent ability.

Clarkia breweri BEAT gene (benzyl alcohol acetyl transferase for benzyl acetate production) was inserted into lisianthus petals to induce fragrance (Noman et al., 2017).

Abiotic and biotic stress tolerance: Breeding for stress resistance/tolerance in ornamental plants is difficult due to a lack of resistance genes (Azadi et al., 2016). In Dendranthema grandiflorum cv. Shinba, three N-methyltransferase genes, CaXMT1, CaMXMT1, and CaDXMT1, were introduced. The findings indicated high Botrytis cinerea resistance.

Rosa sp. is particularly vulnerable to cold stress. The Medicago gene MtDREB1C was used to convert R. chinensis Jacq. Transgenic plants performed well at freezing temperatures, indicating an increase in low-temperature tolerance (Noman et al., 2017).

Shelf-life enhancement: Reduced autocatalytic ethylene synthesis by suppressing genes involved in the ethylene production process, such as ACO (ACC oxidase) or ACS (1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid synthase), has been shown to extend the existence of fruit vases. Silencing the ACO gene resulted in transgenic carnation plants with delayed petal senescence (Noman et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The floriculture industry will benefit from traditional breeding methods combined with biotechnological tools. As a result, scientists and researchers in ornamental horticulture around the world should take advantage of biotechnological advances.

Technologies combined with advanced omics research will help to advance floriculture research and industry in the near future, resulting in more improved traits.

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